

BLUE ECONOMY AMIDST THE INTER-AGENCY ENVIRONMENT TOWARDS SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT

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ABSTRACT

Despite being controversial terms and presenting many misunderstandings, *blue economy* and *sustainable development* are closely related and are at the very center of the global agenda. Due to the complexity of the actors involved in achieving and promoting both agendas, there is often a diversity of public and private actors at different levels (local, national, regional, and international), which often drives the need to promote these agendas through *inter-agency cooperation*. From this context, we intend to analyze how these three concepts dialogue with each other, as well as to reinforce the need to consider them together in the analysis of the blue economy agenda. We conclude that although the agenda is currently experiencing a new momentum, through Agenda 2030 (particularly due to the visibility through SDG 14) and the UN Ocean Decade, there are still many misperceptions and confusions about the concepts, which end up translating into inappropriate and limited policies from the point of view of the industries and relevant countries.

BACKGROUND

Seas and ocean represent a significant portion of the Earth, congregating a diversity of marine fauna and flora whose richness is not even fully known or mapped by society. Precisely because of this and considering the projections for population growth in the coming years and the pressure on natural resources and onshore economic activities, there is growing tension on the new potential and as yet unknown economic opportunities associated with the marine and ocean environment.

However, it is important to note that from an academic and public policy design point of view, this environment has often been overlooked or in some cases ignored. As a result, there is no political,

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normative, and regulatory framework at different levels of government and internationally that accounts for the complexity of dealing with the marine environment. This becomes particularly complex given the diversity of actors and stakeholders involved in activities directly and/or indirectly related to the seas and ocean; although they should often act or be governed by joint regulations, they often do not act in partnership or cooperation networks at all.

“UN-Oceans is an inter-agency mechanism that seeks to enhance the coordination, coherence and effectiveness of competent organizations of the United Nations system and the International Seabed Authority, in conformity with the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea, the respective competences of each of its participating organizations and the mandates and priorities approved by their respective governing bodies.” [1]

From the standpoint of international architecture, it is true that recent efforts have shown a movement toward more solid and robust planning of this environment. Through different modalities such as participation, focal points, meetings, work programme and reporting [2], the creation of UN-Oceans dates back to 1993 when the UN agencies dealing with oceans and coastal issues formed the Subcommittee on Oceans and Coastal Areas of the Administrative Committee on Coordination (ACC SOCA) in 1993 to present a coordinated and comprehensive view of UN agency activities in support of Chapter 17 of Agenda 21 (no contexto do “Earth Summit”, de 1992) [3].

More recently, the relevance given to the seas and the ocean in the long-term agendas of the United Nations (UN) both in Agenda 2030 (2016-2030), particularly through Sustainable Development Goal 14 (SDG 14), and in the UN Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development, also known as the “Ocean Decade” (2021-2030).

In 2020, the Ocean Conference was supposed to be held in Lisbon. Notwithstanding, it had to be postponed due to the conjuncture of the COVID-19 pandemic. As described on the official conference website:

“On 9 September 2021, the General Assembly adopted the draft decision (A/75/578) entitled “2022 United Nations Conference to Support the Implementation of Sustainable Development Goal 14: Conserve and sustainably use the oceans, seas and marine resources for sustainable development,” by which the Assembly decides to convene the Conference from 27 June to 1 July 2022 in Lisbon, Portugal and that the Governments of Kenya and Portugal shall retain co-hosting responsibilities.” [4]

Thus, we are now witnessing an international agenda much more related to the sea and the ocean. It now has a close link with the ongoing debate (particularly after 2012) which highlights the economic relevance of the marine environment from the point of view of economic growth and sustainable development. In this sense, the blue economy has also emerged as a scientific research and public policy

agenda around the world as the key to meeting the challenges of humanity in the context of threats, opportunities, and challenges of the 21st century.

RESULTS

Sustainable development, blue economy and inter-agency cooperation are concepts that have appeared frequently on the international agenda, especially when considered such broad, cross-cutting, and multi-stakeholder themes. However, they continue to be quite misunderstood concepts, which leads to confusion in local, national, regional, and international policies to deal with the issues in question.

In this policy brief, the three aforementioned concepts are intrinsically related. From a practical point of view, it is practically impossible to design policies to promote the blue economy disconnected from a broader debate on sustainable development. The same applies to thinking about stimulating the blue economy without considering the inter-agency environment. Therefore, these terms will be briefly discussed to clarify the debate, highlighting some potential practical outcomes for the design of policy-oriented discussions as well as policy implementation.

Particularly post-2015, the concept of sustainable development has guided the entire UN debate. The 2030 Agenda considers, for example, poverty, hunger, economic growth, renewable energy, gender equality, infrastructure, sustainable cities, production and consumption, climate, and the ocean, proposing means of implementation at national, regional, and international levels. Transforming the world through the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development (SDG) considers 5Ps (people, planet, prosperity, peace, and partnerships), 17 SDGs, and 169 associated targets which are integrated and indivisible [5].

SDG 14 focuses on life below water, seeking to conserve and sustainably use the ocean, seas and marine resources for sustainable development. With 10 targets, SDG 14 is the one that most directly addresses the marine environment, which is why it is almost exclusively the only SDG of the 2030 Agenda associated with the issue. Figure 1 presents some data about the challenges associated with SDG 14 pre and post the COVID-19 pandemic, showing the reduced pressure on the marine environment with the

decline in global economic activity. According to the “The Second World Ocean Assessment” [7: 6-7], ‘many countries have developed, or are developing, strategies for growing ocean-based economies (the blue economy). However, an important constraint on the growth of ocean economies is the current declining health of the ocean and the pressures being placed on it.’ In fact, blue economy is a term that has appeared quite a bit on the current agenda, although often lacking a clear meaning or not following the discussion in the specialized literature.

In Economic Sciences, different concepts arise to deal with the issue, such as economy of the sea, marine economy, maritime economy, and blue economy, for example, which makes the debate confusing and

Figure 1 - Figure 1. Conserve and sustainably use the oceans, sea and marine resources for sustainable development [6]

often inadequate. In short, the concept of blue economy incorporates the debate on ocean governance, including topics such as climate change, sustainable development, blue growth, and maritime law [8].

There are two essential milestones in the development of the blue economy agenda: 2012 and 2021 [9]. In 2012, there was a significant increase in publications of scientific papers and reports on the topic, due to the UN Conference on Sustainable Development (Rio+20), held in Rio de Janeiro, Brazil. Declared in 2017 by the United Nations, the ongoing slogan of the UN Ocean Decade is "the science we need for the ocean we want" and seeks to expand the availability of data on a global scale, as well as promote sustainable ocean management [10].

Finally, it is important to highlight that the promotion of this agenda at the global level necessarily and mandatorily requires considering a context of multi-stakeholders and inter-agency actions. Although this debate often stresses the potential of the blue economy in increasing long-term benefits of the sustainable use of marine resources focused on Small Island Developing States (SIDS) and Coastal Least Developed Countries [11], it is important to emphasize its broader role, also considering developed countries and other countries of the Global South.

CONCLUSIONS

To face the challenges of adaptation towards the blue economy, it is mandatory that the different countries and regions consider sustainable development and the diversity of actors, including in this perspective the inter-agency approach. Thus, although there is no standardization in practices and policies among the different countries, it is important to consider the different international cases to serve as a basis for drawing up development plans aligned with this debate, considering issues such as public policies, financing, participation, sustainability, and inclusion.

Bringing this debate involving concepts and policies to the current context, it is essential to understand all the opportunities related to the promotion of the blue economy. Given the need for economic recovery after COVID-19, the strategic role of the activities and sectors of the blue economy [12] grows, especially due to its capacity to generate jobs and income. Therefore, it should not only be an input in global economic recovery plans, but serve as a basis for adjusting the new development routes that are being designed at the moment, considering the current energy transition underway, the agenda for mitigation of greenhouse gases (GEE) and the social inclusion/participation of different actors, whether public and/or private.

RECOMENDATIONS

Clearly addressing the three concepts involved in the analysis of this policy brief means understanding how sustainable development, blue economy and inter-agency cooperation dialogue and influence each other. To this end, it is worth identifying the case of more developed countries and regions in this debate, such as the United States, the European Union, China, and Australia, for example.

In some countries (such as Brazil), it is necessary to have an official public policy to formulate and publish data and policies oriented to the blue economy. As the UN Ocean Decade itself points out, without the data at hand, decision makers, businessmen, entrepreneurs, and politicians will hardly be able to make the right decisions about the future of the blue economy.

Finally, it is important to consider the potential of the blue economy beyond the SIDS and coastal least developed countries only. This agenda often relates to small, coastal, island, and generally least developed countries. Moreover, it is too often limited to the fishing industry. Actors and decision makers need to be clear about the cross-cutting nature of this agenda, which includes countries at different levels of economic development, as well as a diversity of sectors such as shipping, offshore energy, seabed mining, coastal and ocean tourism, as well as sports and leisure.

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